

CYBERSECURITY: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED CYBERATTACK DETECTION METHODS

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Abstract. Today, the cybersecurity landscape is facing an unprecedented increase in the number of cyberattacks, and the need for effective solutions to detect and prevent them is greater than ever. Time is of the essence in detecting cyberattacks. This article proposes artificial intelligence-based detection methods, in particular machine learning and deep learning, for detecting cyberattacks and reviews more than a dozen recent studies. The article provides suggestions on how effective Machine Learning and Deep Learning-based methods are in detecting different types of cyberattacks. Artificial Intelligence methods are compared, taking into account aspects such as which one is better for new cyberattacks and which method is more effective in detecting threats. This article serves as a basis for evaluating AI methods for detecting cyberattacks, assessing the effectiveness and limitations of Machine Learning and Deep Learning-based methods. According to the research results, it is necessary to continuously optimize Machine Learning and Deep Learning-based artificial intelligence methods for detecting cyberattacks.

Keywords: cyber security, cyber attack, artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning

Аннотация. Сегодня сфера кибербезопасности сталкивается с беспрецедентным ростом числа кибератак, и потребность в эффективных решениях для их обнаружения и предотвращения велика как никогда. Время имеет решающее значение при обнаружении кибератак. В этой статье предлагаются методы обнаружения на основе искусственного интеллекта, в частности машинного обучения и глубокого обучения, для обнаружения кибератак и рассматриваются более десятка недавних исследований. В статье приводятся предложения о том, насколько эффективными могут быть методы машинного обучения и глубокого обучения при обнаружении различных типов кибератак. Сравниваются методы искусственного интеллекта с учетом таких аспектов, как какой из них лучше подходит для новых кибератак и какой метод эффективнее в обнаружении угроз. Данная статья служит основой для оценки методов искусственного интеллекта для обнаружения кибератак, оценки эффективности и ограничений методов, основанных на машинном обучении и глубоком обучении. Согласно результатам исследования, необходимо постоянно оптимизировать методы искусственного интеллекта на основе машинного обучения и глубокого обучения для обнаружения кибератак.

Ключевые слова: кибербезопасность, кибератака, искусственный интеллект, машинное обучение, глубокое обучение

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda kiberxavfsizlik landshafti kiberhujumlar sonining misli ko'rilmagan o'sishiga duch kelmoqda va ularni aniqlash va oldini olish uchun samarali echimlarga ehtiyoj har qachongidan ham ko'proq. Kiberhujumlarni aniqlashda vaqt muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu maqola sun'iy intellekt asosidagi aniqlash usullarini, xususan, kiberhujumlarni aniqlash uchun mashinani o'rganish va chuqur o'rganishni taklif qiladi va o'ndan ortiq so'nggi tadqiqotlarni ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolada Machine Learning va Deep Learning asosidagi usullar har xil turdagi kiberhujumlarni aniqlashda qanchalik samarali bo'lishi haqida takliflar berilgan. Yangi kiberhujumlar uchun qaysi biri yaxshiroq va tahdidlarni aniqlashda qaysi usul samaraliroq ekani kabi jihatlarni hisobga olgan holda Artificial Intelligence usullari solishtiriladi. Ushbu maqola kiberhujumlarni aniqlash uchun AI usullarini baholash, Machine Learning va Deep Learningga asoslangan usullarning samaradorligi va cheklovlarini baholash uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, kiberhujumlarni aniqlash uchun Machine Learning va Deep Learning asosidagi sun'iy intellekt usullarini doimiy ravishda optimallashtirish zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: kiberxavfsizlik, kiberhujum, sun'iy intellekt, mashinani o'rganish, chuqur o'rganish

Introduction

It is no exaggeration to say that the development of the digital world, in particular the increase in the efficiency of working with big data and clouds, is an achievement of our time. However, it is also worth mentioning that attacks are also becoming smarter. Traditional security methods, firewalls, IDS/IPS systems are not enough to detect and prevent today's intelligent attacks. Machine learning-based methods have become the focus of new research. Artificial intelligence-based methods, especially deep learning, have opened up new opportunities for data access and improved performance, unlike ML. DL can detect previously unknown threats with its ability to uncover complex correlations within data. DL has made a significant breakthrough in preventing APT attacks. This article reviews the application of DL and ML in detecting attacks in the cybersecurity landscape, evaluates their effectiveness, and suggests future directions.

Background

Cyberspace is a global domain in the world of information systems, and its distinctive feature is the use of the electronic and electromagnetic spectrum for creation, updating, and storage. Cyberspace, with the ability to use the latest technologies, has the ability to exchange information between interconnected networks, in which it can use the data flow as it pleases [1, 2].

Vulnerability is considered a system or defect in cyberspace that allows an attacker to execute malicious commands, gain unauthorized access to the network, or carry out any threat [3, 4].

Threat: - a set of actions aimed at violating security, and is considered an asset that has negative consequences in terms of its impact [3, 5].

A cyberattack is an aggressive act that primarily targets computer systems, networks, or data. Typically, cyberattacks involve a well-planned and synchronized sequence of steps [6]. Cyberattacks are divided into different categories based on the scope of the attack (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Types of Cyber attacks

The definition of cyberattacks is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Definition of Cyberattacks [7]

Attack type	Definition
DDOS	This type of attack aims to flood the system's resources with unnecessary requests, so that the system is unable to respond to legitimate requests due to the resource overload. DDoS attacks use multiple computer systems as a source
XSS	This type of attack uses third-party web resources to execute scripts in the victim's web browser.
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat: If an individual or group gains unauthorized access to a network and this goes unnoticed, important data can be lost.
Botnet attacks	This type of attack is a compromised computer network that is remotely controlled by an attacker to carry out coordinated malicious actions.
Phishing	This attack involves tricking individuals into divulging sensitive information, such as login credentials and financial data, by masquerading as trustworthy in electronic communication. It's a prevalent method for attackers to gain unauthorized access to personal or corporate data
Malware	It is designed to damage computer systems and data, and malware includes viruses, Trojans, worms, and ransomware.
MitM	This type of attack is when data between two legitimate users is stolen, modified, corrupted, or simply observed by another illegitimate user.
Ransomware	This type of attack is considered a financial threat by holding data hostage, encrypting victims' data and demanding a ransom to decrypt it.
Zero-Day Exploit	Refers to an attack on or before the vendor's first or zero day. These attacks exploit vulnerabilities before they are patched.
Insider threat	Insider Threats stem from individuals within an organization who misuse their authorized access to the company's systems and data.
Password attack	A password attack involves trying to crack a user's password using methods like Brute-Force, Dictionary, Rainbow Table, Credential Stuffing, Password Spraying, and Keylogger attacks, including phishing for passwords.
BEC	These types of attacks target employees with financial authority to trick them into sending money to the attacker's account.
Crypto-jacking	This type of attack secretly uses the victim's computing resources to mine cryptocurrency, posing a hidden threat by draining organizational network resources.

There are several methods for detecting and eliminating the scope of attacks and threats in the field of cybersecurity, and artificial intelligence-based methods are of great importance in terms of efficiency due to their rapid analysis when working with large amounts of data. Artificial intelligence-based approaches in cybersecurity are classified as machine learning and deep learning. These methods have the ability to monitor in real time and continuously train to adapt to new attacks, which increases the effectiveness of detecting attacks in cybersecurity.

Machine Learning in Cybersecurity. Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that uses data and methods to mimic the way humans learn. Machine learning models fall into four categories: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning (Figure 2):

Figure 2. Machine Learning techniques

Supervised learning is a type of machine learning that learns a function that matches an input to an output based on input-output pairs [8].

Unsupervised learning is a type of machine learning that analyzes a data set without human intervention, and relies on data [8]. This type of machine learning is used to extract generative features, identify structures, and group results.

Semi-Supervised learning is a type of ML that combines labeled and unlabeled data to improve the accuracy of predictions. It uses a small amount of labeled data combined with a large amount of unlabeled data to improve the accuracy of training [9].

Reinforcement learning allows software to automatically evaluate optimal behavior in a given environment to improve its performance [10].

In cybersecurity, supervised and unsupervised machine learning algorithms are used to detect cyberattacks.

Figure 3 represents machine learning algorithms that used for cybersecurity.

Figure 3. Machine Learning algorithms

Deep Learning in Cybersecurity. Deep learning is a branch of machine learning that solves problems through multiple layers, which achieves high accuracy and predictive performance. In cybersecurity, deep learning-enhanced solutions are increasingly being used to detect attacks [11]. Several deep learning algorithms and models are widely used to detect cyberattacks (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Deep Learning algorithms

Literature Review

AI-based systems excel in real-time analysis and decision-making, and they use big data to do so. With the increasing number of AI-based threats, the need for big data analytics in cybersecurity is increasing. The use of AI can be used to achieve both time and cost savings [12].

Gaur and Gujral’s research focuses on evaluating ML classifiers for early detection of DDoS attacks on IoT devices. They used the CICDDoS2019 dataset to obtain results from their proposed system. The use of Extra Tree and Anova on classifiers such as RF, DT, KNN, and XGBoost showed an accuracy of 98.34%. This device can detect DDoS attacks early and also lay the foundation for strengthening security in cyberspace [13]. Soliman, Oudah, and Aljuhani propose a Deep Learning-based attack detection system in their research. The proposed solution involves the use of SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) to reduce the feature size using SVD and process the dataset. The ToN_IoT dataset was used to obtain the results of the proposed system and achieved 99.99% accuracy in binary classification and 99.98% accuracy in multi-class classification. This study makes a significant contribution to cybersecurity by providing a robust solution for detecting cyber attacks [14].

Atawneh and Aljehani study the application of DL in phishing detection mechanisms. They used models such as CNN, LSTM, RNN and BERT to detect fake emails and achieved 99.61% accuracy using these models. This study highlights the DL-based cybersecurity techniques against phishing threats [15]. Imtiaz N, etc, in their research work, applied DL methods to detect attacks in IoT systems. The research work used three different datasets, and the proposed XIoT solution showed 99.34% accuracy on the KDD CUP99 dataset, 99.61% accuracy on the UNSW NB15 dataset, and 99.21 accuracy on the Bot-IoT dataset [16]. Reddy SaiSindhu Teja and Shyam developed a DoS attack detection system for cloud systems in their research work. The OCSA algorithm was used in this system, which gives good results in terms of precision and recall values in the system and reduces the data size. Using the benchmark dataset, they achieved 98.18% precision and 94.12% accuracy values, which is a novelty in the field of DoS attack detection in cloud computing systems [17].

Results and discussion

This section reviews and analyzes research findings on AI-based methods for detecting cyberattacks in 2024. This analysis includes results and discussions on the sections listed in the “Research Sections” (Table 3). This analysis and answers to the questions are prepared based on specific indicators and

assessments, which can be an effective result in the development of a system against cyberattacks in the future.

ML models used in Cyberattack detection

The section ML models used in Cyberattack detection presents the latest solutions. These selected studies are summarized and the main details and results are presented in Table 4

DL models in Cyberattack detection

Research studies that incorporate proposed DL-based solutions in cyberattack detection are summarized in Table 5. This research paper uses new models and architectures based on DL algorithms such as CNN, RNN, LSTM. This analysis serves as an important tool in opening up new opportunities for researchers.

Table 3. Research section topics

No	Research results section
1	ML models used in cyberattack detection
2	DL models used in cyberattack detection
3	ML models limitations in cyberattack detection
4	DL models limitations in cyberattack detection
5	Future recommendations for the ML model in detecting cyberattacks
6	Future recommendations for the DL model in detecting cyberattacks

Table 4. Researchs conducted on detecting cyberattacks based on ML methods

Research title	Cyberattack type	Method, algorithm and model type	Used dataset	Results	Future plans
Azeem M, Khan D, Ihtikhar S, Baswazeer S, Alzahrani M. [20]	Malware	ML based on TFIDF	UNSW-NB15	Acc: 97,68%	Investigate Hidden Markov Models
Singh A, Shabargatti A, Jena MA, Manvi S. [21]	Phishing	LR, RF	Phishing dataset from Kaggle	Acc: 92%	Expand data, increase the scope of detection
More S, Idrissi M, Mahmoud H, Asyhan AT [22]	Enhance IDS	LR, SVM, DT, RF	UNSW-NB15	F1: 97,80%	Testing with network traffic data
Talpur F, et al [23]	DDoS	Optimization algorithms with ML	KDD Cup 99, CIC-IDS 2017	Acc: 99,99%	Implementation and tuning
Aljehane NO, et al [24]	NID	FFO and PNN	UNSW-NB15	Acc: 99,79% Specificity: 99,88% MCC: 98,72%	Complexity
Mohsen F, et al [25]	Intrusive Applications	CTMF	Google Play Store Data	Acc: 77,919%	Resource-intensive, time consuming dataset preparation
Wei Z, Rauf U, Mohsen F [26]	Insider Threat	Hybrid Detection ML	CERT r42	Acc: 98,48%	Real-time implementation
Prasad A, Chandra S [27]	Botnet	ML, Network Traffic Analysis	Live botnet attack dataset	Acc: 99,8%	Challenging deployment on resource-constrained devices

Table 5. Researchs conducted on detecting cyberattacks based on DL methods

Research title	Cyberattack type	Method, algorithm and model type	Used dataset	Results	Future plans
Abbas S, et al. [28]	Cyber attacks	DNN, CNN, RNN	CICDiOT2023	Acc: 96,56%	Explore real-time cyberattack detection system integration
Alzahranı IR, Alafi R. [29]	Ransomware	Ebola optimization search algorithm	Dataset including ransomware samples	Acc: 99,88%	Combining Ebola optimization with DL for improved detection in IoT devices
Yaras S, Dener M. [30]	DDoS	CNN, LSTM	CICIoT2023 TON_IOT	Acc (CICIoT2023): 99,995% Acc (TON_IOT): 98,75%	Optimize parameters, develop cost-efficient IDS
Psychogios K [31]	Intrusion in network traffic	CNN, LSTM, attention models	UNSW-NB15	F1: 91%	Explore additional DL architectures for improved prediction accuracy
Devendran R, Turakmani AV. [32]	Cyber attacks	LSTM with chaotic Honey Badger optimization	TON_IOT NSL_KDD	Acc (TON_IOT): 98,76% Acc (NSL_KDD): 99,65%	Hybridize HBO with other techniques
Yun X, et al. [33]	Attacks on DL based-IDS	DLL	NSL_KDD CIC-IDS2018	Acc: 71,9%	Explore robust methods against attacks
Asiri S, et al. [34]	Phishing	Hybrid methods with URL extraction and DL model	Phishing URLs and benign URLs dataset	F1: 99%	Expand dataset, refine models, focus on URL paths

According to the results of the research studies analyzed above, the limitations of ML and DL methods in detecting attacks and suggestions for optimizing the proposed methods in the future are presented in Tables 6 and Table 7.

Table 6. Used ML and DL methods limitations

Type	Limitation
Machine Learning for Cyber Attack Detection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vulnerability 2. Adaptability 3. Complexity 4. Large datasets required 5. Scalability
Deep Learning for Cyber Attack detection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vulnerability 2. Dataset requirement 3. Regular updates 4. Delayed real-time detection 5. Complex algorithms 6. Resource constraints 7. Labeled data shortage

Table 7. Future recommendations for both learnings

Type	Future Recommendations
Machine Learning for Cyber Attack Detection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Integration of emerging technologies 2. Combining RL with other techniques 3. Improving the robustness of AI models 4. Development of a new detection system:
Deep Learning for Cyber Attack Detection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advanced neural architectures 2. Real-time and online learning 3. Efficient learning techniques 4. Hybrid models 5. Scalable and distributed learning

Conclusion

This study reviews AI methods used in cyberattack detection. The main focus is on improving the efficiency of systems based on ML and DL algorithms in cyberattack detection. Studies show that although AI-based methods are more effective and faster in detecting attacks, they require high computational resources and a set of knowledge that needs to be constantly updated.

The article focuses on the role, algorithms, and approaches of DL and ML in cyberattack detection. The study presents analytical tables on the effectiveness, detection capabilities, limitations, and future updates of DL and ML-based methods. This research work can serve as an important basis for applying AI approaches to a specific type of cyberattacks. The results of the research work show that it is necessary to apply and optimize AI algorithms in cyberattack detection.

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